

SETTING OF BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS FOR SECOND-ORDER PARTIAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Abstract

In order to fully study a physical process, in addition to the differential equations describing this process, it is important to study its initial state and its state at the boundary of the field where the process takes place. Below, the setting of boundary value problems for second-order partial differential equations is briefly described.

Key words: differential equation, initial condition, boundary condition, Dirichlet condition, solution, correct problem.

We know that any mechanical and physical problems are always given with initial conditions and it is of fundamental importance. In the process of mathematical modeling, the real problem itself is reduced to ordinary or partial differential equations or a system of equations. Below we will look at some of the processes that lead to partial differential equations.

Let us assume that the state of some process is represented by the vector $u(r,t)$ in the domain of space $R=R(r)$. Let the initial value $u=u_0$ at the initial moment of time $t=0$ and the exact values of the vector u at all values of time t on the surface d of the sphere R be known. Let us ask to find the vector u at all values of time t at all internal points of the field R . We find such a state of the process by solving the equation $du/dt=Lu$ according to the given initial values, where L is an algebraic operator for ordinary differential equations, and a spatial differential operator for differential equations.

If it represents the position of the mesh vector in the spatial position of the medium, then L consists of differential operators [6]. As for the hydrodynamic process, it is possible to express the flow of both stable (specific time derivatives are zero) and unstable ideal heat-impermeable fluids, as well as the flow of fluid around various bodies under different conditions, through a system of closed equations. The set of solutions of this system of equations is very wide. Based on the conditions of the given problem, it is necessary to set the conditions (boundary and initial conditions) that allow choosing the desired solution, that is, a boundary problem is created [4].

In the initial state, some parameters of the environment at the moment of time $t=0$ (for example, displacements, velocities, density, hydrodynamic pressure

values) are given (it is often assumed to be at rest)[3]. One of the factors that form the basis of differential equations with particular derivatives is the additional conditions corresponding to them in addition to the equations themselves. For hyperbolic and parabolic type equations, initial conditions representing the initial state of the environment or system with respect to the free variable t time are introduced. Boundary conditions are introduced for x, y, z coordinates.

In the case of thermal processes, for example, they describe the temperature distribution at the boundaries of the environmental research area. In problems with elliptic equations, time t does not take part, only boundary conditions for coordinates x, y, z are introduced in it, and the problem itself is called a boundary problem. If the boundary condition represents the boundary distribution of that function, then this condition is called the Dirichlet condition. If this condition expressed by the derivative is written on the boundary of the computational domain, then this condition is called Neumann's condition, where the unit normal placed on the boundary of the n th domain is normal. If the boundary condition is formed from a combination of both of the above boundary conditions, then it is called a mixed boundary condition[1].

The solutions of the equations of mathematical physics depend on the setting of the problem representing the initial and boundary conditions. First of all, the solution to the given problem must exist and be unique, and secondly, this solution must be stable (a small change in the solution corresponds to a slight change in the conditions). If the solution to the given problem exists, is unique and stable, then this problem is called a correctly posed (correct) problem.[5]

In practice, there are many ways to solve the above boundary problems, for example, the method of characteristics, the method of separation of variables, the method of resources, and the methods of approximate calculation. Some methods give the analytical expression of the solution of the equation (the problem posed to it), the second one only shows the existence of the solution, and the third one gives the numerical value of this solution. Even sometimes it is necessary to use different methods to find the solution of different problems for one equation.[2]

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